

IEA WIND TASK 52

GENERAL MEETING 2025 - KASSEL

PAVANA GMBH

Annika Baltzer

Facts about Pavana GmbH

Consulting, services and assessments for wind energy

- → Established in 2017
- → Accredited laboratory according DIN ISO IEC EN 17025
- → ~60 employees in several countries, main location Husum
- → subsidiary PAVANA Polska Sp. z.o.o., Koszalin

Reference countries

Measurement equipment

- → 120+ LiDAR units
- → ~ 50 met masts up to 160 m
- → Verification and R&D tower (200m) in the north of Germany and in South Africa

Services

- → Energy yield calculations ,suitability studies, Layouts,
- → Noise and shadow flicker studies, environmental studies
- → Wind measurements
- → Project management support, hybrid energy solutions
- → LiDAR verifications
- → development of German and international guidelines

Motivation

Why PAVANA in the OEMs on challenges panel?

- → Link between manufacturers and practical applications.
- → Interest in a practical approach to the use of LiDAR stand alone measurements
- → Participation in various committees
 - IEC
 - FGW
 - BWE (German Wind Energy Association)
- → Intensive work with LiDAR data in comparison to a 200m met mast and in hundreds of stand-alone LiDAR measurements carried out

LiDAR-Verification

Janneby – Verifications at 200 m

-> Janneby – 200 m max.

-> 10 measurement heights

- 200 m to 20 m in 20 m-steps
- 2 anemometer and 1 wind vane each height
- 3 additional ultra sonics

-> Main wind direction SSW – WNW

-> 2 LiDAR-Pads ~ 75 LiDARs in parallel

Challenges

And how we could overcome them

- → Clearer guidelines that open up for LiDAR stand alone measurements
 - What measures are needed to ensure LiDAR sufficiency?
- → Low data availability – increase LiDAR data availability
 - Questioning common industry standards
 - Applying deep learning quality control algorithms
 - Intensive cooperation with manufacturers
- → LiDAR TI
 - Are there application areas where the measured TI is already useful?

Thank you for the attention

Questions & contact

Contact us:

www.pavana-wind.com

Annika Baltzer

HEAD OF DEPARTMENT LIDAR VERIFICATION

✉ baltzer@pavana-wind.com

☎ +49 4841 8944 234